

THE COMPACTION BEHAVIOUR OF UN-CURED PREPREGS

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Keywords: CFRP, Compaction, Prepregs, Optical microscopy, Resin flow.

ABSTRACT

This study has characterised the compaction behaviour of toughened prepregs which is needed to better understand and optimise the composite manufacturing process. It aimed to cover conditions from all the stages of advanced composite manufacturing: fibre deposition by automatic fibre placement machines, hot or room temperature debulking, and consolidation in autoclave. During these operations the material experiences a wide range of processing parameters: pressure, load rate, temperatures, and boundary constraints. In these conditions toughened prepregs, exhibit complex rheological behaviour with diverse flow and deformation mechanisms at various structural scales.

This paper presents a new methodology for compaction testing and property identification for extraction of material parameters which will be used for the generation of analytical and numerical models.

1 INTRODUCTION

The composite manufacturing industry faces various challenges which are related to understanding and controlling material behaviour throughout the chain of production processes: fibre deposition, debulking, consolidation, and curing. Optimisation efforts are currently concentrated on decreasing debulking times, preventing fibre path and impregnation defects, controlling fibre position/orientation, eliminating resin rich zones, reducing the weight of the component, and avoiding costly consolidation tooling where possible. Understanding the fundamental mechanical behaviour of prepregs is crucial for optimising the composite processing parameters and defect mitigation.

Fibres impregnated with multi-phase toughened resin present a complex system. The compliance of the fibres and inertia of viscous matrix makes prepregs susceptible to fibre-matrix motion. Upon curing the fibre path and impregnation defects strongly influence the composite's performance. Toughening introduces an extra phase to the material and, as a consequence, increases the complexity of the prepreg systems. The presence of a thermoplastic phase substantially increases the range of resin viscosity in the temperature processing range (up to five-six orders of magnitude [8]), changes surface topology and the mechanical properties of ply interfaces, impacts on flow and deformation mechanisms. Thus, it is fundamentally important to understand how the material deforms during the processing operations to ensure that fibres are uniformly enveloped by matrix and remain in the right position and at the right orientation.

Depending on applied conditions, the compliant fibrous network and viscous matrix can exhibit various flow and deformation mechanisms [7]. Two major factors in consolidation are bleeding/percolation flow, which is typical for low-viscosity thermoset resins, and shear/squeezing flow, mostly observed in consolidation of thermoplastic prepregs. In bleeding the pressure gradient causes resin flow relative to the fibres with limited through thickness movement. Thus, the resin escapes from the laminate without shifting fibres in plane but accompanied by fibre bed compaction.

In squeezing flow the system deforms as an incompressible fluid and fibre-matrix system moves transversely to the fibre and compaction directions.

Aside from bleeding and percolation flow, there are other deformation mechanisms. One of which is associated with the surface roughness of prepregs. The filaments of pure resin connecting the plies prior to consolidation are subjected to squeezing flow when prepregs are compacted [11]. As the consolidation progresses the surface area of engaged filaments is increased leading to a better inter-ply contact and, potentially, entrapment of air between plies. Fibre path defect formation can also be considered as the mechanisms of local non-uniform consolidation where plies first lose the adhesion locally and then twist either around the original fibre axis (defect known as “fold”) or around the transverse direction (defect known as “wrinkle”). Another mechanism of deformation of highly viscous materials under applied pressure includes fibre jet-out [1] but it is rarely seen in practice unless very high levels of pressure are reached.

The type of mechanism depends on various factors including resin viscosity, instant fibre volume fraction, pressure distribution, load rates, and constraints of the material. The mechanisms of flow in toughened prepregs may be switched within one processing step or through the entire chain of steps where a wide range of parameters is observed. Three main steps in automated composite processing are:

- (1) High speed deposition (up to 1m/sec [4]) of thin tapes at relatively low temperature and moderate pressure imposed by a soft silicone roller. In the course of deposition the material in front of the roller (so-called “nip point”) is heated to increase tack at the nip point and so aid deposition quality.
- (2) Slow debulking of stacked laminates at elevated temperature and atmospheric pressure. Once laid down, the deposited material is regularly debulked at room or at elevated temperature (30-90°C) to evacuate air and close the tolerance gaps between slit tapes.
- (3) Consolidation of material in autoclave under high pressure, high temperature followed by resin vitrification and subsequent curing.

The characteristic values of parameters in these processes are summarised in Table 1.

	Automatic fibre deposition	Hot/cold debulking	Consolidation in autoclave
Temperature, °C	30-40	20-90	20-180
Pressure, MPa	0.1-0.2 [i]	0.1	0.7
Pressure rate, MPa/sec	up to 7	Slow	Slow
Characteristic dimensions	Tapes 6-12 mm in width, prepreg- roller contact length 30 mm [ii]	Component size	Component size
Time scale	0.03 sec	Hours	Hours

Table 1. Indicative parameters of prepreg processing

In a preliminary study [7] it was observed that the transition between the squeezing and bleeding flow is likely to occur around 60°C, which corresponds to the regime of hot debulking and the first stages of autoclave consolidation.

Many structural features are directly influenced by this flow transition. For instance, heating to an elevated temperature prior to consolidation may prevent the closure of gaps between tows. Upon subsequent compaction the resin may bleed out rather than push fibres into those gaps. The early bleeding flow can also close the pathways for vacuum, preventing air removal and leading to void entrapment. Lukaszewicz and Potter [10] carried out intra-ply void analysis of prepregs using sequential grinding of specimens mounted in resin to achieve a representative number of cross sections. In order to reduce the cross section bias, Hernandez et al. [5] studied the effect of cure cycle on inter-laminar void distribution via X-ray computed tomography (CT). They found void percentages of 2.1% at resolutions of 4µm/voxel and 2.0% at resolution of 11µm/voxel using a cure cycle consisting of a single temperature ramp to 180°C at a rate of 10°C/min.

There are various philosophies of testing the prepregs and pre-impregnated preforms aimed at identifying material properties. The specificity of one or another technique is largely determined by

the assumed flow mechanisms and the correspondent requirements of the models for which tests are used to generate input data. Gutowski et al [3] introduced a model for low viscosity resins which was validated by carrying out compaction experiments with resin pressure measurements presenting the total material behaviour of pre-impregnated systems as a superposition of elastic fibre bed response and resin pressure. This model requires the tensor of transverse permeability, the resin viscosity, and compaction response of dry fibres as an input. Lukaszewicz and Potter [9], investigating the behaviour of toughened prepreg in conditions of AFP, and assumed time independent response of the material at high strain rates. The properties of an elasto-plastic model were then found by extrapolating the results of relaxation tests to high strain rates.

Most of the percolation and shear flow models are based on incompatible assumptions with regard to compressibility, fibre movement, and resin flow. Since these models have traditionally been applied to different classes of materials, the need for a transitional model has rarely been stated. However experimental data shows that a transitional model is needed. For example Hubert and Poursartip [6], testing toughened and low viscosity prepregs on curved tools with bleed and non-bleed bagging conditions. They clearly demonstrated that both squeezing and percolation flows can act concurrently. Neglecting one or another may lead to significant error in thickness estimation, resin pressure, fibre volume fraction, and features of micro-architecture (gaps, resin rich zones).

This paper suggests a new experimental methodology designed to:

- Explore the compaction behaviour of uncured prepregs under processing conditions consistent with all the stages of composite processing: Automatic Fibre Deposition (AFP), cold or hot debulking and consolidation. The focus of the study is on prepreg consolidation, the transitions between the flow mechanisms, size effects, and the limit states.
- Investigate the feasibility of deriving macro-properties from a small scale coupon tests involving minimum of material and experimental efforts and assess the size effects in uncured material. Various laminate configurations are investigated to address the scale-effect issues;
- Generate data for simple extraction of material parameters in a robust procedure covering all the temperature, pressure, pressure rate ranges in pre and post-bleeding conditions for a 3D hyper-viscoelastic model by Belnoue et al. [2].
- Show a qualitative study on the void content after compaction after room temperature debulking and at elevated temperatures to investigate feasibility of reducing hot debulk times.

1.1 Materials and samples

Two toughened aerospace grade prepreg systems developed by Hexcel® were investigated, IM7/8552 with nominal ply thickness of 0.125 mm and IMA/M21 of nominal ply thickness of 0.184 mm. These two systems represent characteristic material toughening strategies. In the IM7/8552 carbon fibre/epoxy system, dissolved thermoplastic toughening is dispersed within plies throughout the bulk phase of the resin. The IMA/M21 system is designed to preserve an extra layer of thermoplastic particles as a distinct interleaf between the plies during processing. The thermoplastic phase is introduced to address the common problem of composite brittleness as it enhances the fracture toughness of the laminate. At the same time thermoplastics affect processing characteristics of prepregs. Toughening elevates the prepregs viscosity, changes inter-ply friction, and the morphology of prepregs as, for example, shown in detail by Lukaszewicz and Potter [10] for IMA/M21. As the result, the flow and deformation mechanisms significantly evolve.

Following [7] the experimental program departs from compaction testing in Dynamic Mechanical Analyser (DMA) to cover a wider range of applied pressure rates in a controlled environment. The DMA has relatively low limits on maximum applied load and hence, this imposes constraints on the composite dimensions required to bring sample to sufficiently high pressure. This also has minor influences on the maximum applied loads in the test program. The effective pressurised area of samples was limited to 15mm x 15mm, which corresponds to 0.26MPa of nominal pressure – this exceeds the pressure experienced by prepregs in AFP and debulking processes but is lower than the limit pressure in autoclave consolidation. Yet, as will be shown further, it covers the range where

changes in thickness are most important. Pressure rates that could be implemented by DMA in flat compaction range could achieve 0.1 MPa/s.

The theory of shear flow [12] suggests that for a Newtonian incompressible fluid under no-slip conditions the apparent viscosity of the squeezing material η_a (taken as the ratio between applied pressure and through-thickness strain rates) is proportional to the initial aspect ratio of width to thickness ratio $(w_0/h_0)^2$. It is important to explore whether this feature is intrinsic to toughened prepregs, exhibiting elements of both shear and percolation flow and where the inter-ply conditions do not necessarily provide the no-slip interface conditions. To explore the size effects, different configurations of 16 plies laminate were investigated: Cross-ply (CP), $[90/0]_8$; Blocked-ply (BP), $[90_4/0_4/90_4/0_4]$; and Semi-blocked (SB), $[90_2/0_2/90_2/0_2]_2$. Additional scaled up tests were implemented in a standard hydraulic testing machine for an effective area of 30 x 30 mm, keeping the thicknesses the same as for the 15 x 15mm specimens.

One of the major requirements of the test is to reproduce ply-interaction conditions of a representative prepreg element, e.g. tape, within the laminate. Simple square shape specimens tend to lose a fraction of material from underneath the pressurised area due to transverse spreading as the plies are squeezed in perpendicular directions and load is only transmitted through the area shared by neighbouring plies. Therefore the plies are laid up in the form of a crucifix to allow excess material for this spreading (figure 1). Specimen lay-up was undertaken in standard clean room conditions following standard lay-up procedures. The thicknesses for laid-up specimens were ~2.2 mm for IM7/8552, and ~3.2 mm prior to testing.

Figure. 1 Plan view of baseline and scale-up specimens with cross section view of lay-up.

1.2 Test program

Baseline tests were carried out using a Metravib 2000 Dynamic Mechanical Analyser (DMA) following an iso-thermal load-controlled compaction programme as described in [7]. Scale-up specimens were tested using an Instron 8801 with temperature controlled hot plates transferring the load and temperature to the sample. Specimens were loaded in two regimes: a slow monotonic loading, and a ramp-dwell regime where the fast application of load is followed by longer intervals of constant load. In both these cases, baseline specimens were loaded to 60 N in 1200 seconds, although the ramp-dwell program included five steps with the increment load of 10 N starting with 20N at the first step. The scale-up specimens, were loaded to 240 N in 1200 seconds. The ramp-dwell program had an increment load of 40 N starting with 80 N at the first step. The baseline samples were tested at temperatures of 30°C, 40°C, 50°C, 60°C, 70°C, 80°C and 90°C, the scale-up specimens were tested at 30°C, 60°C, and 90°C.

At the onset of the load ramp in the baseline case the rate reaches 24.5 N/s which for the sample dimensions translates to ~0.1 MPa/s. This is comparable to the load rates seen in AFP deposition. The time interval for the dwell at pre-set constant loads was set to 240 seconds.

The elastic response in the through-thickness direction presents only a theoretical interest. It is not a dominant mechanism and does not affect any other compaction mechanisms. This study is focused on material reaction that leads to permanent irreversible deformations in the system.

A thin resin release film was applied between the loading plates and the specimens. This film minimises friction between the plate/tool surface and the specimen. There was a greater emphasis on the ramp-dwell loading condition due to the requirement for model calibration and the need for understanding the material behaviour under time dependent conditions.

A small lower case 's' denotes the test has been performed under slow monotonic loading e.g. BPs denotes a blocked ply layup tested under slow monotonic loading. Cases without the lower case 's' indicates ramp-dwell conditions.

After testing, the specimens were cured with no applied pressure to enable polishing, microscopic examination and X-ray CT analysis. To measure the transverse expansion of plies in CP samples, three measurements along the upper and lower surface plies were averaged over all specimens for a given temperature. Widths of the ply blocks were obtained in BP and SB specimens via X-ray computed tomography (CT) scans and averaged over all the specimens tested at a given temperature.

Voids are important defects that can form during compaction and inside resin pockets in areas of fibre wrinkling. While microscopic examination allows high quality measurement of voids in a cut section, the in-plane void dimensions can vary considerably. Characterisation of the voids in the scale up specimens was therefore obtained via X-ray CT using thin strips cut from the cured specimens. The scanned object is represented as a set of voxels, where they are visualised by manual selection of a grey threshold value separating the solid from the air/voids. It is widely accepted that there is some error in determining the volume of smaller segmented voids due to selection of the voxel thresholds, which can potentially register intermediate grey scale values between the air and the material. So this analysis gives more of a qualitative study rather than a quantitative one.

2. Test Results

2.1 Baseline Compaction Testing

In general, the compaction response of the prepregs follows characteristic trends for all the sample configurations and both the examined materials (figure. 2). Each subsequential step generates a smaller displacement increment both on the loading and dwell/creep stages. For a given maximum load and loading regime, the compaction deformations steadily increase with temperature up to 70°C. Beyond this temperature, all the thickness-pressure curves start to converge and little or no further thickness reduction is seen beyond certain pressure/temperature (figure. 3a - NB: CP IM7/8552 shows a somewhat different trend but the deformations are much smaller than in any other configurations). This thickness level will be referred here as the compaction limit. It is important to define another term which describes the final configurations of all specimens and not just those which have reached a compaction limit, this terms will be referred to as a 'degree of compaction'. This describes the final state of the specimens for which the extent of squeezing or bleeding may differ. It is expected that there will always be some combination of the two mechanisms.

Figure. 2 Thickness evolution using the baseline ramp-dwell program: (a) BP and CP IM7/8552 (b) BP and CP IMA/M21.

The degree of compaction and compaction limit shows scale sensitivity that appears to be dependent on sample configuration, sample size, and material system. The observed deformation pattern of BP samples suggested that compaction limit is relatively insensitive to resin viscosity at high temperatures. However the degree of compaction after the full duration of the tests is dependent on the full range of temperatures and hence also resin viscosity up to a certain threshold value of temperature. There is a pronounced drop in viscosity between 70 and 90°C for BP specimens where the thickness-time curves converge, however for CP specimens of the IM7/8552 material, it is not largely reflected in the curves. It is postulated here that even at low temperatures the samples can approach a compaction limit if sufficiently high pressure is applied or duration of the test is sufficiently long. The presence of such a limit could be interpreted as reaching a state where no further transverse spreading is possible, all applied pressure is therefore borne by the fibres, when the limit fibre volume fraction is achieved, which implies no bleeding.

The behaviour of the two prepreg systems were found to be quite different (figure. 3). The relative evolution of thickness and width in IMA/M21 is smaller compared to IM7/8552 samples. It is suggested that the main reason for this is the morphology of the toughening particles. They form clear interfaces between the plies and, hence, a single ply within a block tends to behave like an isolated ply rather than part of a ply block. However, it was noted that for a very large number of blocked plies the merging of plies and large transverse flow may still occur.

Figure. 3 Absolute thicknesses values for (a) Baseline and scale-up IM7/8552 ramp vs baseline monotonic, (b) Baseline and scale-up IMA/M21 ramp vs baseline monotonic

2.2 Transverse widening and through-thickness compaction

It is important to look at the tendency of prepregs to spread for interpreting the compaction response as it shows the balance between the squeezing and bleeding mechanisms. Transverse widening and compaction limit clearly correlate. Figure 4 shows post-compaction widths for CP, SB, and BP baseline specimens of the IM7/8552 material. The CP samples showed no significant transverse expansion. By contrast BP and SB samples exhibited a significant squeezing flow. The squeezing deformations steadily grow in BP and SB specimens as test temperature increases up to 60-70°C. Samples tested at higher temperatures show no further width increase. Similar to the compaction limit, the widening limit depends on the configuration of the sample and does not depend on resin viscosity and temperature beyond a certain threshold (~70°C). This indicates that the likely reason for the compaction/widening limits is the transition from squeezing to bleeding flow. Invariant behaviour of limit states on resin viscosity at 70-90°C shows that by the end of tests there are greater areas of elevated fibre volume fraction throughout the specimens coupled with a much lower proportion of load being transferred by the resin. However the extent of widening/degree of compaction is dependent on resin viscosity and temperature below the threshold of ~70°C in which compaction/widening limits are not always observed within the given test duration.

The relation between the compaction/widening limits and sample configuration present an interesting phenomenon which has not been extensively discussed in literature. The squeezing fluid theory predicts strong inhomogeneity of strain rate distribution in the condition of no-slip between tool and sample, as a consequence, the strong dependence of the apparent viscosity on the sample dimensions (width-to-thickness ratio). Indeed, CP samples were found to be two orders of magnitude times less viscous than BP specimens. Yet the viscosity alone, does not explain the convergence of the compaction curves to a particular limit value. Shear flow theories do not predict any compaction limit other than the case when sample thickness approaches zero and the apparent viscosity becomes infinite. This observation evidences that the transverse flow may have a certain strain limiter. Barnes and Cogswell [1] observed a similar compaction restraints for reinforced thermoplastics and suggested that twisting of fibres at the flow front may cause the spreading locking.

Figure. 4 Relative expansion of specimens ply widths for IM7/8552.

2.3 History and strain-rate effects

Comparison of slow monotonic and ramp dwell programs (with the same average load rate and maximum load level) was made to assess the effect of strain rates on spreading. Previously it was found that for a very high thickness to width aspect ratio, T700/M21 showed notably different resultant thickness for different loading programs. For the current sample configurations with a lower number of plies blocked together, no notable difference in transverse expansion and the through-thickness compaction of the specimens for slow monotonic loading versus ramp-dwell loading for IM7/8552 was found. Figure 5 summarises the force-thickness baseline curves for the specimens under monotonic loading. Significant difference in thickness of CP and BP samples was observed.

Figure. 5 Shows the variation in thickness with slow monotonic loading for baseline IM7/8552 Specimens (a) CP and (b) BP.

2.5 Scale-up Compaction Testing

Qualitatively, the scale-up tests show a similar material response in comparison to the baseline cases. As with the baseline case, the squeezing behaviour was predominantly seen in ramp-dwell tests for elevated temperatures. The largest proportion of through-thickness deformation occurred during the early stages of the test (at the first load step - fig. 6). There is a notable size effect after compaction the larger samples have greater (~0.1 mm) final thickness compared to the baseline specimens. A greater shear flow was seen in CP specimens of IMA/M21 compared to IM7/8552 even in scale-up tests. The difference was postulated as being due to higher thickness to width of ratio of the ply blocks than in IM7/8552 specimens. Similar to the baseline case, the loading mode (slow or ramp-dwell) did not affect the outcomes in terms of the degree of transverse expansion.

Figure. 6 Scale-up thickness-time curves for ramp-dwell loading (a) IM7/8552 and (b) IMA/M21.

2.5.1 Voids

Generally the voids for IM7/8552 material tend to be elongated and needle-like along the direction of fibres. For IMA/M21 specimens, they tend to be circular as the voids occur at the ply interfaces which have additional toughening particles rather than between the fibres. The imaging, segmentation, and total volume of voids were performed using the software, VG studio max v2.1. Segmentation was performed for each specimen, and divided with colour coding for each 4 ply block in the laminate for all specimens, for ease of visualization (figure 7).

The voids generally tend to be of low thickness with high in-plane dimensions. For M21/IMA specimens they are around 60 micron thick with a ‘diameter’ up to 1 mm. The IM7/8552 specimen tends to contain voids that run along the entire length (parallel to the fibre directions) of the scanned volume, around 9-10 mm, with thicknesses similar to those in the M21/IMA system. The total scanned

volume of the specimens is approximately 9mm x 5mm x 2mm and it is assumed that these volumes are representative of the entire specimen.

The void content is greatest for room temperature consolidated specimens, and decreases with increasing temperature under compaction by conditions consistent with hot-debulking. The inter-ply zones are the main void evacuation pathways. The bar charts clearly show a decreasing trend in the void content on going from un-consolidated to room temperature consolidated states and from 30°C to 90°C (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Segmented CT images of voids in BP specimens, showing each of the 4 ply blocks.

Figure 8. Bar chart of voids in the (a) IM7/8552 and (b) IMA/M21 system as a percentage of the total scanned volume.

2.6 Microstructure of compacted samples

The microstructure of prepregs experience a significant transformation in the course of compaction. An examination of the cross-section of cured specimens clearly highlights the deformation mechanisms. Specimens compacted at high temperature tend to show both reduced void size and reduced volume fraction of low fibre density areas.

A clear interface (fine resin rich layer) between the plies of the same direction prior to testing could be seen. In IM7/8552 BP specimens the inter-ply boundaries merge after compaction (figure 9). The interface was still traceable but its geometry presents a complex irregular path through the thickness of the blocked plies (shown in detail in figure 9). Some distortion of inter-ply boundaries was seen in IMA/M21 specimens, however, the degree of distortion was much smaller (figure 10). The inter-ply layers of thermoplastic particles, which are characteristic of this material system, remained clearly visible. It explains why BP and CP specimens show greater similarity in final thicknesses after compaction than in IM7/8552. The degree of nesting, judged by the distorted geometry of ply interfaces, is higher at elevated temperatures for both materials.

Figure. 9 BP at 90°C for IM7/8552.

Figure. 10 BP at 90°C for M21/IMA.

3. Discussion and Conclusion

The experiments show that both material systems exhibit bleeding and squeezing flow mechanisms. Apart from micrographs the results reveal features expected for both the flow types.

There is a notable size effect in both the in-plane and through-thickness directions for both material systems in which the compaction is dependent on the thickness to width ratio. The incompressibility assumption implies that the applied through thickness strains are equivalent to the transverse strains for a ply or ply block. Thus if the ply thickness increases (for instance in going from CP to BP) the width to thickness ratio is lower hence the transverse strains are greater, explaining the greater spreading behaviour for BP for a given temperature. If the in-plane dimensions increase for a given

configuration then the transverse strains are comparably lower for the same applied through thickness strain.

The observations show that for the test durations and strain rates selected for this test programme, above a certain temperature threshold the compaction and widening limits are independent of temperature and thus viscosity. The compaction curves converge to give a compaction limit above $\sim 70^{\circ}\text{C}$. Below this threshold for temperatures between $30\text{-}60^{\circ}\text{C}$, the degree of compaction is dependent on temperature and viscosity.

The coupled nature of squeezing and bleeding flow in prepregs systems has rarely been discussed in literature. Furthermore, prior to bleeding/percolation modern prepreg materials show important features, which are not covered by standard squeezing flow models. Thus, the experiments reveal a need for a new material description which would:

- describe samples of arbitrary thicknesses by the same governing equation (s)
- explicitly include the geometrical size effects in the formulation
- capture the compaction limits both for squeezing and bleeding material states
- incorporate criteria for the switch from squeezing to bleeding flow
- take into account the strain-rate dependency
- employ material constants which can be derived from the compaction tests
- be at the ply scale, and suited to finite element discretisations of ply dimensions.

Future work will present an effort to address some of these challenges by means of a phenomenological model that takes into account structural behaviour of the material at the ply scale.

A new experimental methodology has been presented here in order to further understand the nature of prepregs during the compaction phase of the manufacturing process. It is shown in this paper how the apparent viscosity of the specimens from two material systems with different morphologies, are highly dependent on the initial geometry of the specimens and the layout. A scaling effect is observed upon increasing the in-plane specimen dimensions.

An evaluation of the microstructure gives very clear evidence of the squeezing flow mechanism through inter-ply distortion between ply-blocks. It also shows how the morphology of the prepreg can have a notable effect on the compaction behaviour. In IMA/M21 the thermoplastic particles may have an inhibiting effect in this flow mechanism however the compaction response of the material still shows clear features of bleeding flow.

From CT scans the precise void content is difficult to quantify in general due to intermediate grey scale values at the void/material boundaries, however generally the void content was $<2\%$ for ramp-dwell compaction specimens at 30 and 90°C . Both CP and BP configurations show a similar level of void content.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been funded by the EPSRC Centre for Innovative Manufacturing in Composites: “Defect Generation Mechanisms in Thick and Variable Thickness Composite Parts - Understanding, Predicting and Mitigation” (EP/I033513/1).

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